
**TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA
ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД
LANGUAGE, EDUCATION, TRANSLATION**

ТА'LIM

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**DIALOGIC FUNCTION OF TRANSLATION IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS
A FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

ABSTRACT

Many of the current problems of translation in the modern conditions prevailing in the field of teaching Russian as a foreign language in the Republic of Uzbekistan are related rather not to the linguistic aspect, but to the translation function. The translation function, in turn, is directly related to the process of understanding, its depth. Today, of all the translation functions (dialogic, transformative, subjective, and others), dialogic is most often the optimal one. The problems of modern translation science are directly related to the fact that the translator often does not take into account the difference in semantic rules and structures, allows himself to be misled when translating realities, lacunae, stylistic techniques, engages in excessive literalism, which is as dangerous for the translator as excessive liberty. Literalism in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language occurs most often when the translator strives to make the most complete use of the information of the translated text, that is, implements the transformative function of translation. Excessive freedom in translation is based on the translator's personal attitude to a particular issue, phenomenon or subject, that is, it is a way of implementing the subjective function of translation. However, a highly qualified translator at the current stage of the development of the science of translation requires the implementation of the dialogic function of translation, in which one of

the main conditions is considered to be the preservation of polyphony – a characteristic feature of high-quality translation and an indicator of understanding of the text in the study of Russian as a foreign language.

Keywords: translation; Russian language; translation function; dialogue; transformation; subjectivity; literalism; authorship; polyphony.

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Filologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent, Rus tili va adabiyoti kafedrası

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RUS TILINI CHET TILI SIFATIDA O'QITISHDA TARJIMANING DIALOGIK FUNKTSIYASI

ANNOTATSIYA

O'zbekiston Respublikasida rus tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitish sohasida rivojlangan zamonaviy sharoitda tarjimaning ko'plab dolzarb muammolari lingvistik jihat bilan emas, balki tarjima funktsiyasi bilan bog'liq. Tarjima funktsiyasi, o'z navbatida, tushunish jarayoni, uning chuqurligi bilan bevosita bog'liq. Bugungi kunda tarjimaning barcha funktsiyalaridan (dialogik, transduser, sub'ektiv va boshqalar) dialogik ko'pincha maqbul bo'ladi. Zamonaviy tarjima fanining muammolari to'g'ridan-to'g'ri tarjimon ko'pincha semantik qoidalar va tuzilmalardagi farqni hisobga olmasligi, voqelikni, lakunani, stilistik texnikani tarjima qilishda o'zini yo'ldan ozdirishga imkon berishi, tarjimon uchun haddan tashqari erkinlik kabi xavfli bo'lgan haddan tashqari so'zma-so'zlik bilan shug'ullanishi bilan bog'liq. Rus tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitish jarayonida literalizm ko'pincha tarjimon tarjima qilingan matn ma'lumotlaridan to'liq foydalanishga intilganda, ya'ni tarjimaning transduser funktsiyasini amalga oshirganda paydo bo'ladi. Tarjimada haddan tashqari erkinlik tarjimonning u yoki bu masala, hodisa yoki mavzuga bo'lgan shaxsiy munosabatiga asoslanadi, ya'ni tarjimaning sub'ektiv funktsiyasini amalga oshirish usuli hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga, tarjima fanining rivojlanishining hozirgi bosqichida yuqori malakali tarjimondan tarjimaning dialogik funktsiyasini amalga oshirish talab etiladi, bunda asosiy shartlardan biri polifonikani saqlash hisoblanadi-sifatli tarjimaning o'ziga xos xususiyati va rus tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganishda matnni tushunish ko'rsatkichi.

Kalit so'zlar: tarjima; rus tili; tarjima funktsiyasi; dialog; transformatsiya; sub'ektivlik; literalizm; mualliflik; polifonik.

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ДИАЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ФУНКЦИЯ ПЕРЕВОДА В ОБУЧЕНИИ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ИНОСТРАННОМУ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Многие актуальные проблемы перевода в современных условиях, сложившихся в сфере обучения русскому языку как иностранному в Республике Узбекистан, связаны скорее не с лингвистическим аспектом, а с функцией перевода. Функция перевода, в свою очередь, напрямую связана с процессом понимания, его глубиной. Сегодня из всех функций перевода (диалогическая, преобразовательная, субъективная и другие), чаще всего оптимальной становится диалогическая. Проблемы современной науки о переводе непосредственно связаны с тем, что переводчик часто не принимает во внимание разницу в смысловых правилах и структурах, позволяет ввести себя в заблуждение при переводе реалий, лакун, стилистических приёмов, занимается чрезмерным буквализмом, который для переводчика столь же опасен, как и чрезмерная вольность. Буквализм в процессе обучения русскому языку как иностранному возникает чаще всего тогда, когда переводчик стремится наиболее полно использовать информацию переводимого текста, то есть – реализует преобразовательную функцию перевода. Чрезмерная вольность при переводе основывается на личном отношении переводчика к тому или иному вопросу, явлению или предмету, то есть является способом реализации субъективной функции перевода. Однако от высококвалифицированного переводчика на современной стадии развития науки о переводе требуется реализации именно диалогической функции перевода, при котором одним из главных условий считается сохранение полифоничности – характерной черты качественного перевода и показателя понимания текста в изучении русского языка как иностранного.

Ключевые слова: перевод; русский язык; функция перевода; диалог; преобразование; субъективность; буквализм; авторство; полифоничность.

Introduction. Translation in the study of Russian as a foreign language is an understanding activity that requires a transordinary knowledge of both one's own and the translated language. The difficulties of translation in learning Russian as a foreign language are especially well illustrated by translations of professional texts, work on them is not only cognitive or communicative, but also spiritual, including a value dialogue, understanding as a being process, and the activity of a specialist.

Knowledge of professional Russian as a foreign language is the ability to speak, read, translate, that is, to understand texts created in this language. However,

translation in the study of Russian as a foreign language, including conditional verbatim, is a completely unique activity that requires an initially conscious correlation of a whole complex of meanings and meanings that flow and "flow" into a huge semantic universe: starting from the semantic universe of man and human life as a whole, semantic universes of cultures of individual groups (peoples, etc.), and ending with the semantic universes of each individual subject — the author of the text [1; 2; 3]. This multitude of universes creates an innumerable number of understanding options in learning Russian as a foreign language, i.e. an innumerable number of possible translations. And if we are not talking about the formal literacy of the translation, then its content accuracy can be very different: there are different levels of translation. Their existence becomes noticeable only beyond the "minimal", machine-based or close to it level of searching for verbatim correspondences. However, in order to speak a particular language "fluently" [4, 91], to translate professional-type texts, to achieve a level of multilateral and multilevel understanding, you need to be able to implement different levels of translation. Meeting with different translation options, we can explore this phenomenon and find ways to form and develop the "art of translation" in the study of the Russian language.

The Problem of the Research. The outstanding theorist V.N. Komissarov wrote: "The translator is forced to understand the translated text more deeply than a "normal" reader, for whom the original language is his native language, usually does. This additional depth of understanding is connected with the need, firstly, to draw final conclusions about the content of the text and, secondly, to take into account the requirements of the translation language" [7, 156]. It seems that the description of the necessary and sufficient level of understanding of the text in the context of translation activity is an important task of translation didactics, the solution of which actually determines the construction of the entire system of teaching written translation. Researchers have long been interested in what level of understanding is minimal and sufficient to perform different types of translation – complete and abstract. It is obvious that an exhaustive description of the parameters of translation understanding is still waiting in the wings. In the present article, an attempt is made to comprehend the problem of additional depth of translation understanding based on the dialogic function of translation.

Literature Review. In the specialized literature, you can find dozens of typologies of levels of understanding of the text. One of the first and still frequently mentioned is the typology of A.A. Smirnov. According to his ideas, the ultimate level of understanding is distinguished by "liberation from the stiffness of verbal formulation" [14, 150]. Upon reaching such a stage, "there is really a mastering of what we have perceived. It literally becomes "its own", is translated into "its own language", undergoes some creative processing" [14, 150]. Obviously, such a depth of understanding is redundant for standard translation tasks. Here is how Yu.N. Marchuk said about it: "Understanding ultimately means being able to act in accordance with what has been said, to act outside the sphere of language, so to

speak <...> Translation, however, does not go so far – in the proper sense, it should reproduce orally or in writing only what is said or written in the input language" [8, 70]. As a result, the translator has the opportunity to transmit even the information that is not fully understood, because the translator acts as if by a template, by analogy, copying the composition of the original and in fact not caring, for example, about how convincing the argumentation is and the presentation of the results is accessible. The fundamental translatability of the "formula of thought" [9, 56] deprives the translator of the need to reach the maximum level of understanding when performing a complete translation. But, of course, one should not expect that the resulting translation text will meet all the criteria of professional translation. The resulting product can be called a "good" translation (B.N. Klimzo's term [6, 17]). The possibility of performing a good translation with incomplete understanding is due to three points:

- 1) from the point of view of the psychology of activity, it is a task from the outside of the speech program;
- 2) from the point of view of the object of activity, this is the information redundancy of the original;
- 3) from the point of view of pragmatics, this is a high cognitive level of the recipient, compensating for the imperfection of the translation product.

These points explain why the translation of texts that are obviously incomprehensible to the translator may be quite acceptable, at least in cases where it is addressed to specialists in the relevant subject area. The thing is that the translator's activity is information–centric [10, 112]. A translator is an impartial person who is not interested in the extralinguistic use of information. Analyzing the text, the translator works precisely and only with information, while the specialist – recipient of the translation turns to the text in search of knowledge [11, 38]. This is a fundamental point to justify a sufficient level of understanding when performing a full translation.

The difference between information and knowledge is pointed out by many researchers. This is how generally recognized Japanese business experts Nonaka Ikudzhiro and Takeuchi Hirotaka write about it: "Firstly, knowledge, unlike information, presupposes the presence of opinions and beliefs. Knowledge is a function of a certain position, point of view or intention. Secondly, knowledge, unlike information, implies action. It is always knowledge "for some purpose." Thirdly, both knowledge and information imply meaning and have a situation-dependent and relative meaning" [5]. And further: "Based on the information, new approaches to the interpretation of events and objects are being developed, previously invisible meanings are being revealed, hidden connections are being revealed. Thus, information is the necessary medium, the material for extracting or creating knowledge. It affects knowledge by adding something to it or modifying it. <...> Knowledge is highly connected with human activity" [5].

Results. Modern practice places very high demands on the quality of translation in the study of the Russian language: along with the simplest, "machine"

translation, there are various variants of the author's conditional literal translation, in which the translator not only seeks to reproduce the translated text as a set of concepts and constructions, but also acts as a co-author of the text, complementing the text that will sound in the new culture, the "overtone" necessary for its understanding. Such addition and transformation are always risky, especially in the study of the Russian language, if artistic texts are translated, multilevel and ambiguous, texts filled with specific for the native-speaking people, certain cultural and historical content, as well as psychological "subtext" specific to the author of the translated text, not always obvious, but somehow present even in professional and scientific texts.

It is very important in translation to catch the author's relational intention in the study of the Russian language, not to transform it, but to reveal it. It is with her that the successes and failures of translations of literary texts are connected. In addition to the transformative intention, which defines the "external" purpose of the text as a means of influencing the reader, it is this "internal" meaning that is important—the light that comes from the text, which should be "translated", that is, preserved during translation. Upon reaching such a stage in the study of the Russian language, the development of the translated language takes place: it literally becomes "its own", is translated into "its own language", undergoes some creative processing [6, 17]. This level of understanding in the study of the Russian language is excessive for most standard translation tasks and at the same time causes difficulties in identifying the "quality of translation" [8, 48]. From the point of view of formal correspondences, such a translation can be assessed as unprofessional, low-quality. Translation is the liberation of the text from the "captivity" of the potentiality of the "semantic universe". It involves understanding the meanings of the text that are most accessible to the translator, as well as their repeated concealment, saturation of the text with subtexts and intertexts that allow the reader of a different and original culture to understand the text in its entirety: the translator in the study of the Russian language marks these hidden texts, places where he found a "grain of truth" or hidden from naive eyes "machine translation" mystery, saw an appeal to the semantic layer, far from the situation directly described. Modern "intertextology" and "narratology" pay special attention to those aspects of meaning that are hidden "between the lines", "in the margins", in "between-texts" and in the "stories" of texts: a competent translator in the study of the Russian language takes into account these implicit meanings as reference. Based on them, he reconstructs the external framework of the text, leaving in it signs — "yellow ribbons" marking the deep meanings that served as the primary basis of the text, still waiting for their "liberation" in the process of reading the translation by an interested reader - the third "co-author" of the text.

Discussion. For the perception and transmission of most of the information, careful linguistic analysis and mastery of the technique of text generation are often enough. Extracting knowledge from the text, strictly speaking, is not part of the translator's task.

The translation of a special text by a translator who does not have an education in the relevant field is commonplace. Analyzing this situation, B.N. Klimzo states: "A professional translator is able to perform a dictionary translation that is fully understandable to specialists" [6, 20].

At the same time, the product of the perception of the text when performing a full translation is a quasi-concept. Translation operations are performed at the level of content, but the meaning of the text as an integral work remains inaccessible. Let us recall that meaning is "a mental representation of a segment of reality formed in the consciousness of an individual as a result of the interaction of the text with the background knowledge of the individual" [6, 17]. Detection (or attribution) meaning is always associated with going beyond the immediate reality of verbal stimuli into the realm of extralinguistic conditions, which "are not verbalizations themselves and are interpreted nonverbally" [8, 49].

Comprehension of the textual meaning presupposes an extreme level of understanding, but, as mentioned above, such a level in many cases is not required by the translator. The verbalization of information by means of another language is always based on the original, according to its "script". The translation attitude to the impartial transmission of information has a full professional justification, because, according to A.I. Novikov, "understanding is a complex intellectual process that does not end at the level of text processing. It continues further at the level of thinking, as a result of which the immediate result of understanding this text, arousing various connections and relationships, "acquires" additional components not only cognitive, but also emotional, subjective, pragmatic nature" [12, 33]. This feature of the understanding process is in conflict with the functional responsibilities of the translator. Indeed, the translator does not need such "additional components", because the expansion of the information volume of the original is regarded as a translation arbitrariness and the most critical mistake.

Let us now turn to the category of full-fledged translation, opposed to "good translation". A full-fledged translation is a product that meets all the requirements for professionally oriented printed literature in the target language. Only an expert translator can create such a product. As B.N. Klimzo explains, a good translation can become full-fledged if "additional work has been done to reasonably eliminate errors and alogisms of the author of the source text, clarify the author, construct equivalents of terms missing in dictionaries, recalculate dimensions" [6, 452].

There is no doubt that a full-fledged translation is based on a deep understanding of the source text. And such an understanding is based with additional depth on high translation professionalism: "The transformation of science and technology into a direct productive force in a society with a division of labor has brought to the fore the need for future translators to acquire professional expertise" [10, 118]. No wonder Douglas Robinson warned: "Never assume that you thoroughly understand the original", "Never assume that you understand the original text so accurately that you can adequately translate it" [13, 203].

What is true for a full-fledged translation is equally true for an abstract translation, with the only caveat that the final product is a convolution of the original. The following observations of A.I. Novikov and N.M. Nesterova are interesting in this regard: "Understanding is what is most common in translation and abstracting, what unites them. However, in each of these cases, a different level of understanding is required. If for translation, as a rule, it is enough to comprehend some sections of the text, then for abstracting it is necessary to have a preliminary understanding of the text as a whole. Only under this condition does it become possible to assess what is the main, essential, and what is secondary, additional in the text. Consequently, the attitude to referencing stimulates such a comprehension and understanding of the text, which leads to the formation of a mental education in the translator's intellect, representing the text as a whole" [12, 8].

Thus, in contrast to a full translation, abstract translation forms in the translator's mind a concept that has sufficient completeness to deploy the content in the target language without repeatedly referring to the original (which is impossible in a full translation).

An additional depth of understanding is necessary for the translator to competently select and compress relevant information.

In general, it should be borne in mind that self-reflection is of great importance in professional translation, which, among other things, is designed to determine what level of understanding is required to create a high-quality translation taking into account the current communicative task. Translation activity is always a multifactorial process. The question of the optimal level of understanding of the translator does not have a universal solution, just as the question of the equivalence of the original and the translation does not have one. The world of professional translation is heterogeneous, but one thing should not be in doubt – a "reckless" translation, that is, a translation performed at a lower level of understanding than is required in the current situation, prevents the rapid dissemination of scientific knowledge, and there is "no hope" for such a translator.

Conclusion. As a rule, the level of translation in the study of the Russian language is associated with the translation function, and that, in turn, with the translator's understanding intention: dialogical, relational or transformative. Most often, the dialogic becomes optimal. At the same time, many not so successful translations are due to the fact that the translator does not take into account the difference in semantic rules and structures, and also allows himself to be misled by the so-called "false friends of the translator", sins with unjustified literalism, which is just as undesirable as unjustified liberty. Literalism in the study of the Russian language is based on the translator's desire to use the text, implements a transformative intention. The freedom of translation is associated with "linking" in relationships and meanings, often as fictitious as the resulting translation is fictitious. Russian translation polyphony is one of the conditions of its richness, and the richness of translation is an indicator of the understanding of the text in the study of Russian as a foreign language.

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